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Review Article

**SPHERICAL CRYSTALLIZATION: AN INNOVATIVE
TECHNIQUE IN THE FIELD OF PARTICLE ENGINEERING**A.V.S.Madhulatha ^{1*}, Ch.V.Suresh², A.Ruchitha³, B.Manikanta³, U.Nani³, K.Madhavi³¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.²Principal, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601³Research Scholar, Department of Pharmaceutics, Chennupati Indo American School of Pharmacy, Narasaraopet, Palnadu(Dt), Andhra Pradesh, pin:522601.**Abstract:**

In the manufacture of tablets, the direct compression method is frequently used. In comparison to the traditional wet granulation approach, this cannot be used with sensitive pharmaceuticals and also has a lot more processing restrictions. Spherical agglomeration is an innovative method for creating pharmaceutical dosage forms that are immediately compressible, the process of spherical agglomeration, which improves the powder's qualities such as particle size, shape, flow characteristics, solubility, and bioavailability of pharmaceutical medicinal ingredients, includes transforming tiny crystals into a spherical shape. The spherical crystallization was improved for use with hydrophilic polymers in order to improve the dissolution properties of hydrophobic drugs. The flow characteristics, particle size analysis, compression, and dissolution behavior of the spherical agglomerates were also improved. Wet spherical agglomeration (WSA) and the quasiemulsion solvent diffusion method (QESD) are the two most used methods for crystallizing spheres. Additionally, these approaches have two additions: the ammonia diffusion system (ADS) and crystallo-coagglomeration (CCA). The neutralization technique is another method used in this procedure. Any of the aforementioned methods can be used concurrently for both crystallization and agglomeration. This article describes the overview of spherical crystallization along with the way of optimizing the processing parameters to get effective spherical agglomerates.

Keywords: *Spherical agglomeration; Quasiemulsion solvent diffusion method; Ammonia diffusion system; Crystallo-co agglomeration*

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INTRODUCTION:

Today the tablet is the most popular dosage form of all pharmaceutical preparations produced. From the manufacturing point of view tablets can be produced at much higher rate than any other dosage form. Tablet is the most stable readily portable and consumed dosage form. The formulation of tablet is optimized to achieve goals. The focus today in the business is better drug delivery concepts, but also makes the simple standard formulations as economical as possible to produce. One of the most economical solutions is to find directly compressible formulations and this is especially at interest for large volume products. These have been renewed interest in examining the potential of direct compression tableting over recent years since in comparison to the used at the more traditional granulation process. Such manufacturing of the tablets involves simple mixing and compression of powders which gives benefits like time and cost saving.¹ Thus direct tableting technique has been widely used successfully for various drugs. But it strongly depends upon the quality of the crystals used. When mechanical properties of the drug particles are not adequate a primary granulation is necessary.

The first step in the formulation is often milling or granulation, in order to provide for better properties for the final tableting or to increase bioavailability. Often very small particles are required in order to increase the dissolution rate, and reach sufficient bioavailability. However, micronisation by milling is extremely inefficient, can cause physical and chemical instability, and produces powders with a wide size distribution and poor flowability. The alternative is to produce quite small crystals directly in the crystallization. In some cases thin needles are produced having a high surface area to volume ratio, but likewise may be quite difficult to handle. An interesting alternative is to manufacture larger particles in situ by agglomeration of the small crystals during the crystallization. In addition, it has been revealed that agglomerates have properties that make suitable for direct compression tableting. Crystals could be generated employing any of the available techniques like sublimation, solvent

evaporation, vapor diffusion, thermal treatment and crystallization from melt precipitation by change in pH, growth in presence of additives or the grinding.² Thus the novel agglomeration technique that transforms crystals themselves directly into a compacted spherical form during crystallization process has been desired.³ The use of spherical crystallization as a technique appears to be efficient alternative for obtaining suitable particles for direct compression.^{4,5}

This technique of particle design of drugs has emerged as one the areas of active research currently of interest in pharmaceutical manufacturing and recently came into the forefront of interest or gained interest due to the fact that crystal habit can be modified during crystallization process which would result in better micrometric properties like particle size those can enhance the flowability of the powder drug and prepared spherical crystals can be compress directly without performing granulation, drying and so many steps those are require in wet granulation and in dry granulation process of tablet manufacturing.

Spherical crystallization: Spherical crystallization is a particle design technique, by which crystallization and agglomeration can be carried out simultaneously in one step and which has been successfully utilized for improvement of flowability and compactability of crystalline drugs.⁶

The various parameters optimized were type, amount and mode of addition of bridging liquid, temperature, and agitation speed to get maximum amount of spherical crystals. These were characterized for micromeritic properties (particle size and shape, flowability), packability (bulk density), wettability (contact angle) and compressibility. It was revealed from the studies that spherical agglomerates exhibited improved solubility, flowability, wettability and compaction behavior.

The Principle Steps Involved In The Process Of Spherical Crystallization⁷

Bermer and Zuider Wag proposed four steps in the growth of agglomeration as shown in figure 1.1.

1.1.1. Flocculation Zone:

In this zone the bridging liquid displaces the liquid from the surface of the crystals and these crystals are brought in close proximity by agitation, the adsorbed bridging liquid links the particles by forming bridge or lens between them. In this zone, loose open flocs of particles are formed by pendular bridges and this stage of agglomeration process where the ratio of liquid to the void volume is low and air is the continuous phase, is known as the pendular state. Mutual attraction of particles is brought about by surface tension of the liquid and the liquid bridges. The capillary stage is reached when all the void space within the agglomerate is filled with the liquid. An intermediate state known as funicular state exists between the pendular and capillary stage. The cohesive strength of agglomerate is attributed to the bonding forces exerted by the pendular bridges and capillary suction pressure.

1.2.2. Zero Growth Zone:

Loose flocs get transferred into tightly packets pellets, during which the entrapped fluid is squeezed out followed by the squeezing of the bridging liquid on to the surface of the small flocs causing pore space in the pellet to be completely filled with the bridging liquid. The driving force for the transformation is provided by the agitation of the slurry causing liquid turbulence, pellet-pellet and pellet-stirrer collision.

1.2.3. Fast Growth Zone:

The fast growth zone of the agglomerate takes place when sufficient bridging liquid has squeezed out of the surface of the small agglomerates. This formation of large size article following random collision of well formed nucleus is known as coalescence. Successful collision occurs only if the nucleus has slight excess surface moisture. This imparts plasticity on the nucleus and enhances article deformation and subsequent coalescence.

1.2.4. Constant Size Zone:

In this zone agglomerates cease to grow or even show slight decrease in size. Here the frequency of

coalescence is balanced by breaking frequency of agglomeration. The size reduction may be due to attrition, breakage and shatter. The rate determining step in agglomeration occurs in zero growth zone when bridging liquid is squeezed out of the pores as the initial flocs are transformed into small agglomerates. Another view process that the rate determining step is the collision of particle with the bridging liquid droplets prior to formation of liquid bridges. The rate is governed by rate of agitation. The strength of agglomerates is determined by interfacial tension between the bridging liquid and the continuous liquid phase, the contact angle and the ratio of volume of bridging liquid and solid particles.

1.3. Application of spherical crystallization in pharmaceuticals⁸:

1. This technique improves solubility and dissolution rate of poorly water soluble drugs.
2. This technique enables crystalline form of a drug to be converted into different polymorphic form thus attaining better bioavailability.
3. This technique improves the flowability and compressibility of crystalline drugs.
4. Masks the bitter taste of drug.
5. Physicochemical properties of drug are dramatically improved for pharmaceutical processes like milling, mixing and tableting because of their excellent flow and packability.
6. It enables subsequent processes such as separation, filtration, drying to be carried out more efficiently.
7. It is also used in preparation of microsponges, microspheres and nanospheres, nanoparticles and micropellets as novel particulate drug delivery system.

1.4. Methods of spherical crystallization:

1.4.1. Spherical Agglomeration method (SA):- Spherical agglomeration involve implications of three different solvents such as good solvent (dissolution medium for drug), bridging liquid (medium which partially dissolves drug and has wetting property) and

poor solvent (solvent which is immiscible with drug substance)⁹. A nearly saturated solution of drug in good solvent is poured in to the poor solvent, provided that the poor and good solvents are freely miscible and affinity between good solvent and poor solvent is stronger than the affinity between the drug and the good solvent, this leads to the formation of crystals immediately. Further third solvent called bridging liquid is added in smaller amount to promote the formation of agglomerates under continuous agitation. The bridging liquid should not be miscible with the poor solvent and must wet the precipitated crystals. As a result of interfacial tension

effects and capillary forces, the bridging liquid act to adhere the crystals to one another forming agglomerates. The spherical agglomeration method has been applied to several drugs, and it has been found that the product properties are quite sensitive to the amount of bridging liquid. Relatively less amount of optimum bridging liquid produces plenty of fine crystals and vice versa. Also the choice of bridging liquid, the stirring speed and concentration of solute are of importance. Higher stirring rate produces agglomerates that are less porous and more resistant to mechanical stress, porosity decreases as the concentration of the solid increases.

Figure 1.2: Steps involved in the Spherical Agglomeration method

Chow et al postulated some general guide lines for the spherical agglomeration of drugs¹⁰.

- For compounds that are water soluble, a water-immiscible organic solvent is used as the external medium and salt solutions of high concentration without common ions can be used as the bridging liquid.
- For compounds that are soluble in one or more organic solvents water is employed as the external phase and a water-immiscible organic solvent as the bridging liquid.
- For compounds that are only soluble in water-miscible organic solvents a saturated aqueous solution of the compound can serve as the external phase and an organic solvent mixture as the bridging solvent.
- For compounds that are insoluble in water or any organic solvents a water-immiscible organic solvent can act as the external phase and a 20% calcium chloride solution as the bridging liquid. In addition, a binding agent

such as PVP or PEG is required for agglomeration since the powders are not sufficiently soluble in the bridging liquids to allow binding through recrystallization and fusion.

1.4.2. Emulsion solvent diffusion (ESD) method or Quasi ESD Method:

In this method the affinity between the drug and good solvent is stronger than that of the poor solvent¹¹. The drug is dissolved in good solvent and dispersed into poor solvent producing emulsion (quasi) droplets, even though the pure solvents are miscible. The good solvent diffuses gradually out of the emulsion droplets into the surrounding poor solvent phase, and the poor solvent diffuses into the droplets by which the drug crystallizes inside the droplets. The method is simpler than spherical agglomeration method, but the choice of suitable solvent is very critical in order to keep the system emulsified and even diffusion of the poor solute into the dispersed phase is difficult.

Figure 1.3: Steps involved in the Emulsion solvent diffusion (ESD) method

1.4.3. Ammonia diffusion method: This method can be used for amphoteric drugs which can not be agglomerated by conventional methods¹². In this method, the mixture of three partially immiscible solvents i.e. acetone, ammonia water, dichloromethane were used. Ammonia water acts as the bridging liquid and as well as good solvent. Acetone is water miscible and bad solvent, thus drug precipitate without forming ammonium salts. Dichloromethane is water immiscible solvents and induce liberation of ammonia. The fraction of ammonia water is the system that exists as an immiscible phase forms droplet. The counter diffusion process across the droplet involves movement of solvent into and ammonia out of the droplet. The droplet collects the crystals as a drug in ammonia water precipitates slowly and growth of agglomerates occurs.

Figure 1.3: Steps involved in the Ammonia diffusion method

1.4.4. Neutralization Method: This method drug is characterized by dissolved in good solvent and placed in the cylindrical vessel with constant stirring¹³. While stirring an aqueous polymer solution along

with a neutral solution is added which neutralize the good solvent and eliciting drug crystallization, bridging liquid is added drop wise with a definite constant rate, which causes agglomeration of crystals.

1.5.Factors affecting the process of spherical crystallization¹⁴:

1.5.1.Temperature :Temperature of the system has considerable influence on the size, shape and texture of the agglomerates. The solubility of drug is influenced by the change in temperature. At higher temperature, the larger agglomerates were produced initially and the equilibrium attained more rapidly than at lower temperature. At lower temperature, it was characteristic that the growth rate of crystals was slow at the initial stage but become faster at the later stage. At low temperature, the initial numbers of crystals produced were greater than a high temperature, the number of nuclei increased with decreased crystallization temperature.

1.5.2.Mode and Intensity of Agitation:The degree of mechanical agitation along with the quantity of bridging liquid determines the rate of growth and size of agglomerates. The mode and intensity of agitation must be optimized. High speed agitation is required to disperse the bridging liquid through the system. The product of high speed shaker blender is usually in the form of irregular agglomerates. When tanks are used as a reaction vessel, more irregular but less spherical agglomerates were obtained. An inclined pan and drum agglomerator facilitated the size enlargement process. Any change in agitation pattern or fluid flow would be reflected as change in force acting on agglomerate, which ultimately affects the shape of agglomerate. Mechanical agitation is the prime variable affecting the process and is necessary to bring the particles into proximity so that the force responsible for agglomeration may become operative. But in some cases increasing stirring rate, may cause

reduction in agglomerate formation due to increased disruptive forces. Higher stirring rates produces agglomerates that are less porous and more resistant to mechanical stress. The extent of mechanical agitation in conjugation with the amount of bridging liquid determines the rate of formation of agglomerate and their final size

1.5.3. Bridging liquid: The properties of spherical agglomerates were influenced by the amount of bridging liquid. Generally the bridging liquid is added in a smaller amount to promote the formation of agglomerates and depending upon the amount of bridging liquid, particles can form either loose flocs or compact pellets.

1.5.4. Solvent : The choice of solvent depends on the solubility profile of drug. A mutually immiscible three solvent system consisting of good solvent, poor or anti solvent and bridging liquid are necessary. Physical form of product i.e. whether micro agglomerate or irregular macro-agglomerates or a paste of drug substance can be controlled by selection of proper solvent proportions. The proportion of solvent to be used is determined by carrying out solubility studies and constructing triangular phase or Scheffe ternary diagram to define the region of mutual immiscibility.

1.5.5. Residence time : The time for which agglomerates remain suspended in the reaction mixture shown significant influence on strength of agglomerates. Optimum residence time for the agglomeration of recrystallized crystals was required. Below the optimized residence time the incomplete agglomeration occurs due to incomplete diffusion of good solvent and bridging liquid from the formed droplets in the dispersion medium. At longer residence time the formed agglomerates were break down and the size of the agglomerated particles decreases. This might be due to the solubilization of the agglomerates by the bridging liquid that diffuses out from them.

1.6. Parameters of pharmaceutical ingredients improved by spherical crystallization technique

Spherical crystallization technique cause improvement of following properties.

1.6.1. Particle Size and Size Distribution: Particle size and shape of pharmaceutical ingredients can be modified by this technique. Usually a large size and spherical shape particle are formed. Size of particles are improved due to the aggregation if particles influenced by the bridging solvent. Similarly, agitation of solvent system during process results in the spherical shape of particles. Particle size and shape of spherical crystals can be determined by using optical microscopy (or) scanning electron microscopy (or) X-ray Powder Diffraction technique.¹⁵

1.6.2. Mechanical Strength: Spherical crystals should posses good mechanical strength as that directly reflects the mechanical strength of compact or tablet. This may be due to increased intraparticle force with in spherical agglomerated crystals. Mechanical Strength can be determined by measuring the tensile strength or crushing strength. The tensile strength of tablets prepared from agglomerated crystals was always higher than the tablets prepared from single crystal at the same compression pressure. This was due to plastic deformation of the agglomerated crystals resulting in greater permanent particle contact and stronger bond force than in case of the original crystals. It has been established that the production of fresh surface by fracturing during the compression process is necessary to expose to air to bind the particles strongly for tableting. If fractured surface is exposed to air for a long time after breaking, no improvement in inter particle bond occurs because of the reduction in free energy of the surface when absorbed with air¹⁶.

1.6.3. Flow Property: Flow property of the material depends on the force developed between the particle size, particle shape, surface texture and surface area. The improvement in the flowability of spherical crystals could be attributed to the significant reduction in interparticle friction, due to their spherical shape and a lower static electric charge. The improvement in the flowability of spherical crystals can be determined by measuring the Angle of Repose or Carr's Index or Hausner Ratio¹⁷.

1.6.4. Packability: Improve packability has been reported for agglomerates prepared by spherical crystallization. The angle of friction, shear cohesive stress and shear indexes are lower then that of single crystals, which can improve the packability of the agglomerates¹⁸.

1.6.5. Compression Behaviour Analysis: Good compactibility and compressibility are essential properties of directly compressible crystals. The compaction behavior of agglomerated crystals and single crystals is obtained by plotting the relative volume against the compression pressure. Spherical agglomerates possess superior strength characteristics in comparison to conventional crystals. It is suggest that the surface are freshly prepared by fracture during compression of agglomerates, which enhances the plastic inter particle bonding, resulting in a lower compression force required for compressing the agglomerates under plastic deformation compared to that of single crystals¹⁹.

1.6.6. Wettability: Wettability of agglomerated crystals by water is investigated by measuring the contact angle of water to the compressed crystals. The wettability depends on the crystallinity and

elementary crystal size of the agglomerated crystals. As the contact angle decreases the wettability increases. Crystals with low crystallinity are more wettable than crystals with higher crystallinity²⁰.

1.6.7. Dissolution Rate and Bioavailability: The dissolution rate and bioavailability of agglomerated crystal depends on particle size, particle density and specific surface area of the agglomerated crystals. It has been elucidated that the dissolution of agglomerates increases as apparent specific surface area increases²⁰.

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